

ENGLISH AS A GLOBAL LANGUAGE

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Abstract: As indicated in the title, this article shows a brief viewpoint of English as an international language, how it becomes a global language, its impact to globalization and other languages. In this article, following statements are described: how the English language is entering to our country; the main role of English in the modern world.

Key words: English, languages, global world, international, different nations

Language is becoming powerful key to find a treasure. Why we need to learn foreign languages? Is it worthy studying international languages? In today's world, everyone must learn at least one language to travel and live in better position. Language represents human's needs, realizations, understandings, communication facilities. We have already known that efficiency of learning English language is rising not only in our country but also all over the world. Every country has its own culture, language, customs and special ceremonies, which are not, repeated other countries. When we learn new language, we not only learn means of communication but we can learn and adopt its traditions.

With the facilities of languages, we will be a person who has different viewpoints. Nowadays, the English language has its special rate of learning in every society and it is becoming whole humanity's international means of communication. You may ask: why do you usually discuss only about English? Why not Russian or French? We may count many causes for this. One of them, many countries have been using this language for many years and many foreign nations speak in this language. Why we need to learn new languages? Definitely, improving and enriching our speech and worldviews. Many scientific experiments explain us that knowing many languages is the legality of an advanced development, a key of success. In addition, knowing one of the foreign languages can open different possibility doors for us. How it would be? Simple example may prove our ideas. In every subject, we come across and see foreign words, which we don't know. If you want to learn about scientific technologies, you should also learn English language. In short, it is very difficult to imagine our life without any languages. Knowing English language well can create facilities to use new advanced technologies. Maybe you know that conferences, which we often see in mess media, are conducted in English language. It proves that language helps everyone to find and gain their position in today's developing society. Most of the younger generation who go to foreign countries to continue their studies should also know the language because almost all the books from every field: medicine, technology, science, tourism, business and so on are written in foreign languages especially-in English language. It has already become a great key for those who wish to work and study in a foreign country. One of the scientific studies prove that many percentages of about (85%) scientific magazines are published in that language.

In order to maintain and strengthen international relationship in technology, medicine, education, tourism, politics, economy English language serves the uniting relations as a global language. When English plays a dominant role in nearly every field in present developing world, why we shouldn't discuss its role as a global language. One of the famous scientists Savid Crystal writes down that: a language becomes the global language for one reason: political power of its people. Its usage is spreading all over the world. You can easily watch films without any translations, may listen to music understand its original version. These are simple advantages of knowing foreign languages. The most surprising thing that when you go to other countries, you can easily tell your necessities to any of the foreigners. Nowadays, our government is also making new decisions about strengthening, learning one of the foreign languages. More attention to the English language because it is such kind of the language that the majority of the population in almost every state of the world can speak and understand. Not far from political field, we also say that many scientific materials have been created in English language. The only requirement we should do to understand and use it in useful way. Before learning new languages, we should know our mother tongue language as well. Because without gaining native and its grammatical categories, it will be difficult to know about another languages. While I was studying, I would sure that every language has somehow similar features with each other. If you learn 1 language and also want to study more languages at the second time you will learn it more quickly than the first. While learning new languages at first we should put clear purpose. Learners every kind of language demands much time as if you go to travel far away, but you cannot realize for what purposes you travel. Why do you go to exactly that place, there is not any necessity of learning languages without aims. If you have clear intention of studying foreign languages you will gain your goals without any difficulties. It seems hard work but after knowing it will be your companion forever and it opens you possibility doors. For studying languages perfectly, we need perfect handbooks. By using this means, we can learn English fast and more effective.

Our first President I. A. Karimov told that: people need spiritual knowledge, as they need water and air. Language-is a shared system, which belongs to certain group or people or society. In today's business and trade also involved a language. How different nations, different companies can contact with each other what do you think? Certainly with the help of a language. It unites all nations in one place. Because of England's rule over different fields such as trade, business, technology and the internet throughout many years. It made English language universals. Today, this language has become the leading role in diplomacy, science, literature. Being a universal language brings everyone together in one section. Knowing and gaining English language creates different advantages in getting a good job in a multinational companies or finding a career or studying abroad, travelling places which you dream seeing about them. Language is a phenomenon that effects human's life. In today's modern English mainly spread around the world at the beginning of the 17th century. Because of the dominance of British Empire throughout the continent and power of the United States of America. Now English language is playing a leading role with comparing other languages. English language is also lingua franca language type it means that people who do not speak one another's target language .United states of America speak this language had always become the center of the attention for every other countries in the world. As USA strengthen and widely used around the world, new fields in technology gave rise to spread language and mess-media Because of this, in today's world, many people try to learn especially English

language. By this, we conclude that language always should be with us. If you learn something. Always repeat your things which you learned, at any given time you can communicate with others without shying, if you use technologies with purposeful and effective, you will find your position in this world. Don't afraid of difficulties. Because, difficulties which you see today, will light up your future life forever.

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